

netWorked Youth Research for **Empowerment** in the Digital society

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Training Actions

WP4_D4.5

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WYRED_WP4_D4.5

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1. Introduction

According to the WYRED project proposal (García-Peñalvo, 2016b, 2017; García-Peñalvo & Kearney, 2016; Griffiths et al., 2017), as part of the WP4 “Networking”, a set of training actions has been developed and implemented to raise awareness among the participants of the ethical issues involved in the project, such as data protection, privacy, safeguarding and other issues.

The work package leader, YEU, developed a set of videos on the topics mentioned above addressed to the different groups of participants. These videos are available for the WYRED platform users according to their profile and age range once they are logged in.

The following videos have been produced.

2. Training actions

- Are you ready for WYRED? WYRED for facilitators
<https://youtu.be/MvCqoR7ZxZ8>
- Are you ready for WYRED? – Children
<https://youtu.be/rmf8Q7gZ8Ls>
- Are you ready for WYRED? - 14-18 years
<https://youtu.be/35WQPe7ImzU>
- Are you ready for WYRED - over 18 years
<https://youtu.be/gg4caJqw7kl>

3. WYRED platform tutorials

General Training actions are available in the WYRED platform (García-Peñalvo, 2016a; García-Peñalvo & Durán-Escudero, 2017; WYRED Consortium, 2017) **help page:** <https://platform.wyredproject.eu/help>

- Access and password recovery
<https://youtu.be/OXz2xF3pIns>
- Are you ready for WYRED? – Children
<https://youtu.be/rmf8Q7gZ8Ls>
- Are you ready for WYRED? - 14-18 years
<https://youtu.be/35WQPe7ImzU>
- Are you ready for WYRED - over 18 years
<https://youtu.be/gg4caJqw7kl>

Training actions for facilitators available in the WYRED platform after the login with a facilitator profile:

Users training actions

- Edit your profile
<https://youtu.be/y0TjQUqV72E>

Facilitator training actions

- Create a new community
<https://youtu.be/IUeNASpg1bk>
- Invite new users
https://youtu.be/Z0eMLNMDI_Q
- Add registered users
<https://youtu.be/9WbUXakwnSM>
- Manage users
<https://youtu.be/BFu0kNcvYxQ>
- Are you ready for WYRED? WYRED for facilitators
<https://youtu.be/MvCqoR7ZxZ8>

Training actions for users available in the WYRED platform after the login:

Users training actions

- Edit your profile
<https://youtu.be/y0TjQUqV72E>
- Are you ready for WYRED? – Children
<https://youtu.be/rmf8Q7gZ8Ls>
- Are you ready for WYRED? - 14-18 years
<https://youtu.be/35WQPe7ImzU>
- Are you ready for WYRED - over 18 years old
<https://youtu.be/gg4caJqw7kl>

The screenshot shows the WYRED platform interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'HOME', 'COMMUNITIES', 'EVENTS -', 'HELP', and 'USER ACCOUNT -'. Below this is a header with the WYRED logo and the tagline 'The platform for the young'. A secondary navigation bar contains 'HOME' and 'HELP'. The main content area is divided into several sections:

- Technical support - WYRED Platform:** A text block explaining that the platform is continuously improved and needs user feedback.
- General training actions:** A section titled 'Access and password recovery' featuring a video thumbnail for 'WYRED Platform tutorials - Access'.
- Users training actions:** A section titled 'Edit your profile' featuring a video thumbnail for 'WYRED Platform tutorials - Edit your profile'.
- Are you ready for WYRED?:** A series of video thumbnails for different age groups:
 - For children (under 14 years):** A video titled 'Are you ready for WYRED? - Children' showing two cartoon characters.
 - For youth between 14-18 years:** A video titled 'Are you ready for WYRED? - 14-18 years' featuring a character pointing to a sign that says 'Pay Attention!' with text about being aware of online actions.
 - For youth over 18 years:** A video titled 'Are you ready for WYRED - over 18 years' featuring a character pointing to a sign that says 'ADVICE'.

4. Referencias

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